

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for KIF5A (Q12840) for use in western blot

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Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)).

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab278079	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT
Abcam	ab306717	-	U-87 MG	<i>KIF5A</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the KIF5A antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab322900**	1113400-1	AB_3698263	recombinant mono	EPR29540-31	rabbit	0.507	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab5628	1081534-6	AB_2132218	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IP, IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP33868_P050	QC3274	AB_841511	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.500	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	92872**	1	AB_3698333	recombinant mono	F2W1W	rabbit	0.000	Wb
GeneTex	GTX103761	40142	AB_11173959	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb
GeneTex	GTX104875	39708	AB_1241009	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb
GeneTex	GTX113761	40142	AB_2037309	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.230	Wb
Proteintech	21186-1-AP	14632	AB_10733125	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.287	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	67009-1-Ig*	10008940	AB_2882326	monoclonal	1A7E3	mouse	1.000	Wb,
Proteintech	84013-4-RR**	23010610	AB_3671581	recombinant mono	241124H1	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IF
Proteintech	84013-5-RR**	23011174	AB_3671582	recombinant mono	241124H5	rabbit	0.400	Wb

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody

Figure 1: KIF5A antibody screening by western blot

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: KIF5A antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of U-87 MG WT and *KIF5A* KO were prepared, and 60 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated KIF5A antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab322900** at 1/1000, ab5628 at 1/500, ARP33868 at 1/500, 92872** at 1/500, GTX103761 at 1/500, GTX104875 at 1/500, GTX113761 at 1/500, 21186-1-AP at 1/500, 67009-1-Ig* at 1/500, 84013-4-RR** at 1/3000, 84013-5-RR** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 117.3 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.